

AN ARCHITECTURE FOR A DISTRIBUTED CLOUD HONEYPOT

Ravula Kartheek

Assistant Professor, Bapatla Engineering College: Bapatla

B. Siva Kanaka Raju

Assistant Professor, Vignan Institute Technology & Science: Hyderabad

Yada.Sindhura

Assistant Professor, Guru Nanak Institutions Technical Campus: Hyderabad

ABSTRACT

DDoS assaults present a significant menace to the Internet. With the increasing prevalence of the Internet of Things (IoT), the DDoS attack has evolved beyond a simple traffic attack. The primary focus of the attack has shifted from the network layer to the application layer. In addition, DDoS attacks utilizing botnets yield more devastating consequences. The objective of this study is to introduce a novel collaborative active defensive framework that combines Honeypot and cloud platform technologies. This framework is designed to identify and protect against future Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) assaults inside the Internet of Things (IoT) context. The framework is capable of detecting and mitigating large volumes of malicious traffic, measured in Terabytes, in real-time.

Keywords: Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) assaults, Botnets, Honeypot, Cloud computing

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I. INTRODUCTION

DDoS assaults present a significant menace to the Internet. Defense mechanisms arise and mature swiftly. Nevertheless, assailants consistently enhance and refine their malevolent techniques, technologies, and instruments to target and deceive these security systems. The DDoS attacks are becoming increasingly intricate and devastating, reaching a critical juncture when innovative technologies and collaborative efforts are required.

This study aims to investigate and suggest a novel active defense framework that utilizes cloud architecture and decoy servers, specifically Honeypots, to identify, protect against, and analyze complex DDoS attacks that are always evolving.

II. BACKGROUND

A denial-of-service assault, often known as a DoS attack, is a type of cyber-attack where the attacker intentionally renders a machine or network resource inaccessible to its intended users. This is achieved by causing temporary or permanent disruption to the services provided by a host that is connected to the Internet [1]. A distributed denial-of-service assault (DDoS attack) occurs when a large volume of incoming traffic overwhelms the victim's system, originating from numerous sources. This renders it exceedingly difficult to halt the attack only by obstructing a one origin.

A distributed denial-of-service (DDoS) assault happens when several systems overwhelm the bandwidth or resources of a targeted system, typically one or more web servers [2]. Such an attack frequently occurs when several hacked computers, such as a botnet, inundate the targeted system with a high volume of traffic. A botnet is a collection of compromised computers that have been covertly designed to execute orders without the knowledge or consent of their owners [3].

DDoS assaults commonly include flooding the victim with an excessive number of packets, specifically targeting vital network resources. This results in the victim becoming inaccessible to genuine users. Complex DDoS assaults involve the transmission of improperly structured packets, which overwhelm applications or protocols on the targeted machine, causing it to become unresponsive or reboot [4]. Contemporary DDoS attacks exhibit greater complexity and potency compared to other forms of cyber-attacks.

Honeypot is a network security technology that serves as an active defense complement. The system has the ability to detect and document assaults, monitor unauthorized access attempts, and block attacks from spreading beyond compromised systems. As the most efficient method of defense against DDoS attacks, it has the capacity to protect a large operating network with a high level of certainty against both known DDoS attacks and new, emerging variations. Furthermore, it can be utilized to ensnare the assailant, allowing for the documentation of the breach to serve as evidence in a judicial proceeding against the perpetrator [5].

However, the newest type of DDoS attacks are on a size and severity that are too big for a single Honeypot to handle. More so, DDoS attacks that use a lot of bonnets can easily hit a few Tbps of traffic.

After this, some cases will be given. This is the same as a DDoS attack in the cloud that uses many spread-out computers, or "bonnets." This means that Cloud-based Honeypots are suggested as a way to deal with cloud-based DDoS attacks if a single Honeypot isn't enough.

III. DISTRIBUTED DENIAL OF SERVICE (DDOS) ATTACKS

A distributed denial of service (DDoS) assault is a type of attack where numerous hosts are used to perform a coordinated denial of service (DoS) attack against one or more targets. This attack operates under a client/server manner. Criminals typically employ several hijacked host computers, known as Botnets, as a platform for their attacks, therefore significantly amplifying the impact of the attack [6]. Distributed denial of service (DDoS) attacks are designed to inundate targets with atypical network traffic, thereby impeding or obstructing authorized network users from accessing network resources. DDoS attacks consume a significant amount of bandwidth in order to target a major adversary, such as a web-based media organization.

These assaults frequently involve the coordination of numerous compromised machines, known as botnets, to simultaneously flood the victim's network with traffic. As a result, the victim's network becomes either useless or experiences significantly degraded performance.

DDoS attacks commonly involve flooding the victim with an excessive number of packets, specifically aimed at disrupting important network resources and rendering them inaccessible to legitimate users. Complex DDoS assaults involve the transmission of improperly structured packets, which overwhelm applications or protocols on the targeted machine, causing it to become unresponsive or necessitating a restart [4]. Contemporary DDoS attacks exhibit greater complexity and potency compared to other forms of cyber-attacks. DDoS assaults can be categorized into three primary classifications [8]:

- Volume-based attacks encompass ICMP floods, UDP floods, and other packet assaults using spoofing. The main objective is to impede the victim's website's bandwidth. These attacks have the potential to surpass the utmost capabilities of most individual defense mechanisms, such as Honeypots. Therefore, this category will be the primary emphasis of this paper.
- Protocol-based assaults including SYN flooding, fragmented packet attacks, Ping of Death, and Smurf attacks. The major target of this type of assault is the server resources, such as the firewall.
- Application layer assaults are a kind of cyber attacks that specifically target online applications. These attacks are known for their high level of sophistication and their ability to cause significant damage.

Figure 1 displays a selection of distinct DDoS assaults from each category. DNS amplification attacks exemplify the Volumetric attack category.

The attacks are directed towards the DNS server. An attack commences by utilizing a falsified IP address and entices a targeted DNS server into responding to a substantial volume of data, so impairing the server's performance [9]. These DDoS attacks typically surpass the limit capacity of most defense mechanisms, including individual Honeypots. As an illustration, GitHub experienced the most severe DDoS attack to date, with a peak attacking load of 1.35 Tbps. Additionally, it holds the record for being the largest and most potent distributed denial of service (DDoS) attack in the history of the Internet [10].

Figure 1 illustrates the classification of DDoS attacks.

Consequently, no individual defense mechanism, such as Honeypot, can effectively handle or even replicate such a large volume of traffic. Cloud computing systems offer a potential solution for combining many individual defense mechanisms, particularly a group of coordinated Honeypots, to protect against DDoS attacks involving large amounts of network traffic. In addition, due to its reliance on computer networks, cloud computing is highly susceptible to DDoS attacks. In their research, the author utilizes Honeypot to reconstruct their cloud computing infrastructure. They convincingly demonstrate that Honeypot is capable of withstanding both known DDoS attacks and new, emerging variations. Additionally, Honeypot offers enhanced legal evidence capabilities.

IV. DDOS AND HONEYPOTS

Active defense is a strategic approach that involves installing various security measures to proactively counter possible intruders. This method relies on the premise that the possible invader being targeted is less competent. Illustrations of this strategy encompass the establishment and utilization of catalogues including reliable networks, devices, and applications, the prohibition of untrustworthy addresses, and the supervision of vendors.

A honeypot is a network security solution that serves as an active defense complement. The system has the ability to detect and document assaults, monitor unauthorized access attempts and hacking actions, and stop attacks from spreading beyond compromised computers. As the most efficient and powerful method of defense against DDoS assaults, it has the capacity to protect our operating network with a high level of certainty against both known DDoS attacks and new, emerging variations in the future. Furthermore, it can be utilized to ensnare the assailant, so enabling the recording of the breach to serve as evidence in a judicial proceeding against the attacker [5].

A Honeypot, in the context of computer security, refers to a deliberately insecure application or server designed to entice and ensnare hackers. The attackers, under the impression that they are targeting a genuine resource, exhibit typical behavior by employing their attack techniques and tools against this decoy site. This enables the defenders to closely observe and monitor the attackers' activities, analyze their methods of attack, and acquire knowledge to develop appropriate defenses for the actual resources [11].

It's just a way to catch strikes, the honeypot. Clifford Stoll's book "The Cuckoo's Egg" was the first to use the term "Honeypot." The Honeypot is also called "a security resource whose value lies in being probed, attacked, or compromised" [12]. In general, a honeypot is a fake system that has been carefully designed to be vulnerable. An ISP, host, or service can be it. The last few years have been good for computer security because Honeypot has been a good place to learn about a lot of different types of malware. Fred Cohen made "The Deception Toolkit" in 1998, which was the first useful honeypot tool. It came out in the late 1990s. Since then, they've been made public and available for business use, especially to get rid of worms and other programs that copy themselves [13].

Honeypots can be categorized as high interaction or low interaction based on the frequency of interaction between the honeypot and the attacker. Furthermore, Honeypots can be categorized into two types: production Honeypots and research Honeypots, based on their intended purpose of deployment. Alternatively, a categorization technique exists that can categorize Honeypots into physical Honeypots and virtual Honeypots, depending on their distinct design schemes [14]. Figure 2 contains a comparison.

Characteristic	High-Interaction Honeypots	Low-Interaction Honeypots
Advantages		
1. Comprehensive examination	Offers comprehensive analysis of attacker methodologies and resources	Constrained to fundamental interactions, lacking in-depth investigation
2. Advanced threats	Identifies complex and previously unknown vulnerabilities and assaults	Mainly detects typical attacks
3. Real-world simulation	involves replicating actual systems, which in turn attracts more sophisticated attackers.	On the other hand, it simulates specific services but may be less realistic overall.
4. Comprehensive telemetry	Gathers substantial information on attacker activities	Offers minimal telemetry
Disadvantages		
1. Complexity	Demands greater allocation of resources for both initial setup and ongoing maintenance	More convenient to implement and oversee
2. Risk	The possibility that attackers may exploit a compromised honeypot to launch attacks on other systems	Reduced risk as a result of minimal engagement
3. Cost	Increased operating expenses resulting from the need for additional resources	Reduce expenses associated with operations
4. Detection	Experienced attackers may be able to detect it	More difficult to detect

Figure 2 illustrates the benefits and drawbacks of high- and low-interaction honeypots.

When compared to intrusion detection systems (IDS) and other technologies, Honeypot technology is comparatively straightforward, allowing network operators to easily gather information on intruders. Figure 3 provides a comparison between Firewalls and Honeypots. Figure 4 provides an additional comparison between IDS and Honeypots.

The primary characteristics or elements of Honeypots include network spoofing capability, port redirection, alerting, data collecting, analysis, and control.

Network Spoofing: The Honeypot is a fake system that is meant to be attacked. It seems to be turned into a real host that criminals want to attack. It pretends to be an operating system or a vulnerability on the spoofed host, creates fake network data, and encourages hackers to attack.

Port Redirection: Honeypots use port redirection to make a system that is supposed to be running look like it has services but doesn't. Most of the time, the Port Redirector module sends information from a production server to a deception server.

Alerting: A honeypot has an important alerting module that lets managers and other security experts know right away.

Characteristics	Firewall	Honeypot
Purpose	Deter unlawful entry	Entice and ensnare hostile individuals
Detection	is the process of filtering network traffic	Monitoring interactions with a honeypot.
Response	Filters and eliminates harmful network traffic.	Records and examines the actions of an assailant

Fig. 3. An Analysis of Firewalls and Honeypots

IDS	Honeypot
Identify and identify unauthorized access attempts to a computer network	Draw in and ensnare malevolent individuals
Examines network data for irregularities	Observes and records interactions with honeypot
Triggers notifications, maybe obstructs the flow of vehicles	Records and examines the actions of the attacker

Figure 4 illustrates a comparison between Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) and Honeypots.

Honeypots are used to regulate network traffic in order to prevent unauthorized individuals from exploiting the spoofing system as a means to launch attacks on other systems. They also manage the system's data stream covertly, evading detection by the intruder.

Once an intruder gains control of a system, they may establish a network connection and acquire toolkits to carry out targeted assaults. To do so, the intruder must be granted certain "legitimate" permissions.

Data collection and analysis involve monitoring and recording all activities that enter and depart the Honeypot. The goal is to gather as much information as possible in order to analyze the attacker's strategy and purpose. Placing the recorded data on the host of the Honeypot would make it vulnerable to detection by intruders.

Dwiyatno and his colleagues [15] employed Honeyd Honeypot to identify Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) assaults in their study. The empirical findings demonstrate that the data acquired by Honeyd Honeypot has the capability to promptly identify and mitigate Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS)

assaults. [16] employed virtual Honeypots to efficiently identify DDoS attacks. [17] We implemented Honeypot-based redirection technology to successfully block DDoS assaults and ensure Quality of Service (QoS) at the Internet Service Provider (ISP) level. This technology also allows us to maintain normal response times for legitimate users even during DDoS attacks.

By doing a thorough examination of past research, it becomes evident that DDoS attacks are undergoing significant transformations. One of the groups that has been expanding is the botnet group, which is made up of Internet of Things (IoT) devices. Mirai IoT botnets have become widely recognized as representative of new botnets [18].

Moreover, the utilization of public resources to execute the intensified reflection attacks of DDoS attacks has become increasingly prevalent. Modern attackers generate an enormous amount of spam traffic to target networks and their services, employing collaborative attacks and hybrid attacks. A solitary Honeypot is insufficient to handle the escalating influx of attack traffic.

Furthermore, the occurrence of coordinated and cooperative DDoS attacks hinder the ability of a standard Honeypot to promptly and effectively identify them. Thus, it is imperative to create a collaborative Honeypot architecture that can efficiently handle a substantial amount of DDoS traffic while concurrently performing extensive detection, data capture, and analysis duties. This paper proposes a cloud-based collaborative Honeypot system.

V. CLOUD HONEYPORT INFRASTRUCTURE

CISCO has created a new idea of Cloud Security in Cloud services [19]. It provides security measures for the Cloud, safeguarding people, data, and applications within the cloud [19]. The primary functions of Cloud Security encompass

1. The detection and prevention of threats.
2. Safeguard the Cloud and its users
3. Ensure the security of Cloud data and applications

Cisco Cloudlock is a cloud-native cloud access security broker (CASB) and cloud cybersecurity platform within the CISCO Cloud Security framework. It provides security for users, data, and applications in software as a service, platform as a service, and infrastructure as a service [20]. Unfortunately, the current CISCO Cloud Security does not offer Honeypot services. In addition, the building cost of CISCO Cloud Security is very high, making it unaffordable for most small to medium-sized organizations. Therefore, this study begins by introducing a cloud-based Honeypot scheme, known as Cloud Honeypot, to fulfill its distinct security capabilities and provide it as an active defense security service to small and medium-sized businesses. The Cloud Honeypot will enhance its ability to combat DDoS attacks involving high volumes of traffic, like the previously stated instance that reached a bandwidth of 1.35 Tbps [10]. This architecture can utilize a "Cloud of Honeypots" to counteract DDoS attacks by employing a "Cloud of Botnets". This research aims to develop a novel business model that will facilitate the widespread adoption of Cloud Computing principles. The findings of this research will be documented in a separate written paper. The Cloud Honeypot's design and business concept are currently being patented. Hence, certain sensitive information will not be addressed in this document. Figure 5 depicts a comprehensive Cloud Honeypot architecture.

Figure 5 displays the initial architecture of a cloud honeypot.

Furthermore, the discovery of hybrid assaults, exemplified by the Dyn's DNS server attack [21], has revealed the existence of two distinct techniques of attack. Due to their complexity, hybrid attacks are challenging to fully capture and analyze using a single Honeypot. To address this issue, Cloud Honeypot divides the conventional Honeypot framework into four interconnected components, which are executed and synchronized utilizing virtualized technologies. Each analysis module will produce an individual system log, which will be subsequently consolidated and analyzed by the Cloud Honeypot.

Furthermore, it is imperative to incorporate a novel module, specifically a DDoS feature detection module, to accurately identify and match DDoS features. This will effectively mitigate false positives and enhance the analysis of forthcoming DDoS attacks. Figure 6 shows a modified Cloud Honeypot.

Figure 6 displays a revised cloud honeypot architecture.

To enhance the security of the new cloud Honeypot and enhance the system's capacity, dependability, and scalability, this architecture implements several Cloud sub-Honeypots throughout the entire production system. The enhanced solution will enhance the Honeypot's ability to confound the DDoS attacker and, in addition, efficiently integrate with IDS to enhance detection performance. Furthermore, any suspicious traffic identified by the Intrusion Detection System (IDS) will be randomly assigned to an accessible Cloud sub-Honeypot for the purpose of containment, data capture, and analysis. Upon capturing and examining the assault traffic, the ultimate system logs will be transferred to cloud storage for subsequent investigation and analysis. Figure 7 illustrates the design of the primary processes of Cloud Honeypot.

Figure 7 displays a diagram of a cloud honeypot.

VI. INITIAL IMPLEMENTATION AND PROTOTYPING

The initial phase of the project involves utilizing a simulator, specifically EVE-NG [22], to construct a network framework centered around Honeypot detection. Furthermore, the Kali Linux system [23], a software specifically designed for penetration testing, is employed to mimic a DDoS attack. This is done in order to assess the effectiveness of the Honeypot server and analyze its detection response. To create a more accurate simulation of the experimental environment, the network architecture was constructed using the EVE-NG simulator. The Honeypot server was built using the VMware platform, namely vSphere [24]. To simulate the DDoS attack, the Kali Linux system was utilized. The initial phase of the tests has been concluded and the experimental Cloud Honeypot is depicted in Figure 8. Figure 9 illustrates a simulated assault on a complete network server using Kali Linux.

Figure 8 displays the initial stage of the experimental cloud honeypot.

```

8086/tcp open 0-s-11
8087/tcp open simplifymedia
8088/tcp open radan-http
8089/tcp open unknown
8090/tcp open opsmessaging
8291/tcp open unknown
8443/tcp open https-alt
9000/tcp open cslistener
9200/tcp open wap-wsp
9898/tcp open monkeycom
10000/tcp open snet-sensor-mgmt
10617/tcp open unknown
20000/tcp open dnp
31337/tcp open Elite
49152/tcp open unknown
49153/tcp open unknown
49154/tcp open unknown
49155/tcp open unknown
49156/tcp open unknown
MAC Address: 00:0C:29:27:26:CD (VMware)

Nmap done: 1 IP address (1 host up) scanned in 2.76 seconds
root@kali:~# hping3 192.168.192.135 -i ul
HPING 192.168.192.135 (eth0 192.168.192.135): NO FLAGS are set, 40 headers + 0 data bytes
len=46 ip=192.168.192.135 ttl=128 DF id=13196 sport=0 flags=RA seq=0 win=0 rtt=7.9 ms
^[[A^[[A^[[A^[[A^C^C
--- 192.168.192.135 hping statistic ---
1 packets transmitted, 1 packets received, 0% packet loss
round-trip min/avg/max = 7.9/7.9/7.9 ms
root@kali:~# nmap -sS 192.168.192.131
Starting Nmap 7.70 ( https://nmap.org ) at 2021-05-23 03:27 EDT
Note: Host seems down. If it is really up, but blocking our ping probes, try -Pn
Nmap done: 1 IP address (0 hosts up) scanned in 0.55 seconds
root@kali:~# hping3 192.168.192.131 -i ul
HPING 192.168.192.131 (eth0 192.168.192.131): NO FLAGS are set, 40 headers + 0 data bytes
^C
--- 192.168.192.131 hping statistic ---
1 packets transmitted, 0 packets received, 100% packet loss
round-trip min/avg/max = 0.0/0.0/0.0 ms
root@kali:~# hping3 -c 5000 -d 150 -S -w 64 -p 80 --flood 192.168.192.130
HPING 192.168.192.130 (eth0 192.168.192.130): S set, 40 headers + 150 data bytes
    
```

Figure 9 depicts a simulated assault on a complete network server.

Figure 10 illustrates the Cloud Honeypot successfully identifying the Kali Linux Server and its malicious activities on the local area network (LAN), and promptly notifying the relevant events.

ID	Start	Dur.	Pro.	Sens.	Name	Visitor	Description	Received	Sig. Mes.
123	2021/5/23 8:29:20.254	0.000	TCP	80	IS	192.168.192.134	Syn Scan	XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX	
122	2021/5/23 8:29:20.254	0.000	TCP	80	IS	192.168.192.134	Syn Scan	XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX	
121	2021/5/23 8:29:20.254	0.000	TCP	80	IS	192.168.192.134	Syn Scan	XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX	
120	2021/5/23 8:29:20.254	0.000	TCP	80	IS	192.168.192.134	Syn Scan	XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX	
119	2021/5/23 8:29:20.254	0.000	TCP	80	IS	192.168.192.134	Syn Scan	XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX	
118	2021/5/23 8:29:20.254	0.000	TCP	80	IS	192.168.192.134	Syn Scan	XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX	
117	2021/5/23 8:29:20.254	0.000	TCP	80	IS	192.168.192.134	Syn Scan	XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX	
116	2021/5/23 8:29:20.254	0.000	TCP	80	IS	192.168.192.134	Syn Scan	XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX	
115	2021/5/23 8:29:20.254	0.000	TCP	80	IS	192.168.192.134	Syn Scan	XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX	
114	2021/5/23 8:29:20.254	0.000	TCP	80	IS	192.168.192.134	Syn Scan	XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX	
113	2021/5/23 8:29:20.254	0.000	TCP	80	IS	192.168.192.134	Syn Scan	XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX	
112	2021/5/23 8:29:20.254	0.000	TCP	80	IS	192.168.192.134	Syn Scan	XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX	
111	2021/5/23 8:29:20.255	0.000	TCP	80	IS	192.168.192.134	Syn Scan	XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX	
110	2021/5/23 8:29:20.255	0.000	TCP	80	IS	192.168.192.134	Syn Scan	XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX	
109	2021/5/23 8:29:20.255	0.000	TCP	80	IS	192.168.192.134	Syn Scan	XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX	
108	2021/5/23 8:29:29.208	0.000	TCP	80	DOS Att.	192.168.192.134	DOS Attack	Connections: 250(0...	
107	2021/5/23 8:29:20.255	0.000	TCP	80	IS	192.168.192.134	Syn Scan	XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX	
106	2021/5/23 8:29:20.255	0.000	TCP	80	IS	192.168.192.134	Syn Scan	XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX	
105	2021/5/23 8:29:20.255	0.000	TCP	80	IS	192.168.192.134	Syn Scan	XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX	
104	2021/5/23 8:29:20.254	0.000	TCP	80	IS	192.168.192.134	Syn Scan	XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX	
103	2021/5/23 8:29:20.254	0.000	TCP	80	IS	192.168.192.134	Syn Scan	XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX	
102	2021/5/23 8:29:20.254	0.000	TCP	80	IS	192.168.192.134	Syn Scan	XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX	
101	2021/5/23 8:29:20.254	0.000	TCP	80	IS	192.168.192.134	Syn Scan	XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX	
100	2021/5/23 8:29:20.254	0.000	TCP	80	IS	192.168.192.134	Syn Scan	XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX	
99	2021/5/23 8:26:47.225	0.000	ICMP	0	ICMP Ec...	192.168.192.254		Id: 297930[A]Seq 0...	
98	2021/5/23 8:26:46.128	0.000	ICMP	0	ICMP Ec...	192.168.192.254		Id: 297930[A]Seq 0...	
97	2021/5/23 8:06:07.160	0.000	TCP	901	TCP Syn...	192.168.192.134	Syn Scan		
96	2021/5/23 8:06:07.160	0.000	TCP	7800	TCP Syn...	192.168.192.134	Syn Scan		
95	2021/5/23 8:06:07.160	0.000	TCP	4004	TCP Syn...	192.168.192.134	Syn Scan		
94	2021/5/23 8:06:07.157	0.000	TCP	1090	TCP Syn...	192.168.192.134	Syn Scan		
93	2021/5/23 8:06:07.157	0.000	TCP	1034	TCP Syn...	192.168.192.134	Syn Scan		
92	2021/5/23 8:06:07.157	0.000	TCP	2008	TCP Syn...	192.168.192.134	Syn Scan		
91	2021/5/23 8:06:07.157	0.000	TCP	3260	TCP Syn...	192.168.192.134	Syn Scan		
90	2021/5/23 8:06:07.157	0.000	TCP	49158	TCP Syn...	192.168.192.134	Syn Scan		

Figure 10 displays the results of the penetration study.

In the second phase, virtual technology will be employed to create several platforms that replicate each aspect of Honeypot and combine these platforms to construct a cloud-based Honeypot. Conduct a stress test using Kali Linux.

Subsequent phases will implement a fully functional, limited-scale Cloud Honeypot in an actual setting. Multiple additional DDoS attack tools will be identified and utilized to assess the Cloud Honeypot.

This experiment aims to evaluate the efficacy of Cloud Honeypots in capturing attacks and identifying their effectiveness, while also enhancing the framework's design.

7. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

This study introduces and elaborates on a novel cloud security paradigm utilizing Cloud infrastructure. The analysis began by thoroughly examining the present state of DDoS attacks, with a specific focus on volume-based DDoS operations.

A comprehensive evaluation has been conducted on the most efficient method of identifying and actively protecting against threats, known as Honeybot. The primary issue with current Honeybots is their insufficient processing capacity to effectively handle large-scale DDoS attacks, particularly ones employing Botnets, such as a Cloud-style DDoS attack. Research has shown that while a single Honeybot is unable to handle DDoS attacks that beyond its maximum capacity, a sufficient number of coordinated Honeybots may effectively mitigate this type of DDoS attacks. Given the rapid advancement of Cloud security infrastructure, this study introduces a novel Cloud Honeybot infrastructure and a newly devised commercial model for cloud computing.

The initial phase of the design and execution, which relied on prominent industry simulation software, has been successfully concluded. This paper presents the corresponding sample outcomes. In the upcoming phases of the project, we will focus on enhancing the Cloud Honeybot by improving its collaborating modules, data analysis capabilities, and including additional cooperative sub-Honeybots into its structure. A novel idea of Honeybots as a Service (HaaS) has been introduced and implemented. Further details regarding this development will be presented in an ongoing research paper. The HaaS concepts will be employed to enhance the Cloud Honeybot infrastructure.

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